

Bridging Innovation and Sustainability in Engineering Education: work in progress

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15850324>

Abstract

Institutional models for innovation in engineering education play a critical role in shaping students' mindsets to address complex challenges in their professional careers. Thus, this research focuses on a framework development inspired by student-centered approaches to improve the mindset of bringing theoretical knowledge into practical, sustainable, and innovative solutions in engineering education. The need for this framework is associated with graduates struggling to meet the demands of a rapidly evolving labor market. It reflects a broader global challenge of preparing students to address complex 21st-century issues like climate change and social inequality. A comprehensive literature review revealed that while student-centered approaches have proven effective in fostering creativity and innovation, empirical evidence does not connect these methods directly to sustainability outcomes. Furthermore, this review identified key gaps in aligning engineering education with the competencies required for sustainable development. The research will employ a mixed-methods and practice-oriented approach, incorporating qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques to capture the multifaceted nature of the learning process involving experimental interventions with engineering students. This process involves four stages: literature review, approach design, implementation and evaluation, and framework refining. This work is in progress, specifically in the first stage. The preliminary findings present the first-stage results. Preliminary findings suggest a complementary relationship between sustainability and innovation: sustainability sets the overarching objectives, while innovation provides the tools to achieve them. This relationship is crucial in engineering education, where addressing global challenges demands innovative solutions. Key gaps include fostering an innovation culture emphasizing critical thinking, ethical considerations, social responsibility, active learning methodologies, and effective integration of sustainability and innovation mindset in the outcomes to promote knowledge transfer capabilities. As a result, the design is a challenge-based learning framework that fosters an innovation mindset, nurturing a sustainability vision.

Keywords: student-centered approach; Engineering Education; Sustainability; Innovation.

1 Introduction

In the 21st century, global society faces the dual imperatives of sustainable development and innovation-led transformation. These challenges—exacerbated by environmental degradation, social inequalities, and shifting economic structures—demand a profound rethinking of how knowledge is generated, transferred, and applied. Education, particularly engineering education, is central to this process, as it equips the professionals responsible for shaping technical and infrastructural responses to societal needs. Integrating sustainability and innovation in engineering curricula has thus evolved from a desirable attribute to an urgent necessity.

Sustainability, initially confined to environmental concerns, is now widely recognized as a multidimensional framework encompassing ecological, social, and economic dimensions. Rooted in the Brundtland Commission's definition—"development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987)—the concept has broadened through the adoption of models such as the Triple Bottom Line and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). These paradigms emphasize ethical awareness, long-term thinking, and cross-disciplinary collaboration. Consequently, education systems must promote cognitive knowledge and behavioral and affective competencies aligned with sustainability principles (Blanco-Portela et al., 2017; Wiek et al., 2011).

Simultaneously, innovation has emerged as a fundamental engine for economic and societal development. Schumpeter's (1934) early definition of innovation as "new combinations" of existing resources continues to influence contemporary understanding (Schumpeter, 1942), but has since been complemented by broader, systems-oriented approaches (Freeman, 2008). Today, innovation includes sustainable practices supported by models like design thinking, open innovation, and living labs (Berger et al., 1985; Chesbrough, 2002). These frameworks stress stakeholder co-creation, interdisciplinary work, and iterative learning processes. Tools such as Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs), Innovation Readiness Levels (IRLs), and Social Readiness Levels (SRLs) provide practical frameworks for evaluating innovation maturity and impact, underscoring the importance of systematic assessment in educational and professional domains (Tell & Hoveskog, 2022).

At the convergence of sustainability and innovation lies engineering education, a field uniquely equipped to contribute to sustainable transitions by designing and implementing technological solutions. However, traditional education models, with their emphasis on technical content delivery, may lack the depth required to address the complexity of contemporary global challenges of the contemporary world (UNESCO, 2022). As a response, higher education institutions are increasingly adopting student-centered approaches—such as Problem-Based Learning (PBL), Project-Based Learning (PjBL), and Challenge-Based Learning (CBL)—which promote experiential, collaborative, and ethical engagement with real-world problems (Sukacké et al., 2022). Among these, CBL has gained prominence for its explicit emphasis on systems thinking, ethical awareness, and the involvement of multiple stakeholders in the learning process (Tell & Hoveskog, 2022).

However, the implementation of such pedagogies remains inconsistent across global contexts. In Colombia, for example, while the number of higher education graduates has increased, employers continue to report difficulties in finding adequately skilled professionals, particularly in innovation-related areas (Colombian Private Competitiveness Council, 2023). This reveals a fundamental disconnect between the outcomes of higher education and labor market needs. The Global Innovation Index (WIPO, 2023) further highlights Colombia's slow growth in innovation metrics, attributing this to weak institutional frameworks and limited societal appropriation of knowledge. These trends are mirrored in other countries, underscoring the global nature of the challenge: educational systems are not sufficiently aligned with the evolving demands of a sustainability-driven innovation society.

Given this context, the central research question guiding this study is: How can the development of an innovation mindset be enhanced in engineering education from a sustainability perspective? Addressing this question requires curricular changes and a broader epistemological and cultural shift within educational institutions. It entails a movement from transmissive to transformative education, where students become co-creators of knowledge and meaning, capable of navigating complexity and uncertainty with creativity and ethical responsibility (Mezirow, 2000; Sterling, 2024).

This research advocates for a student-centered approach rooted in co-learning, in which students and educators engage in shared inquiry and collaborative problem-solving. Such environments foster technical and analytical skills, as well as the interpersonal and intrapersonal competencies necessary for sustainable innovation, including empathy, resilience, and systems thinking (Wiek & Lang, 2016). The model emphasizes learning experiences grounded in real-life challenges that reflect societal needs, encouraging students to develop solutions with a tangible and lasting impact (Schönach et al., 2023).

International reference institutions such as UNESCO, the OECD, and the Aalborg UNESCO Centre for PBL have promoted educational sustainability and innovation through policy recommendations, curriculum design, and teacher training (Kolmos & de Graaff, 2014; OECD, 2014). However, the results are present majorly in specific regions of the world. In some developed countries, many institutions lack the necessary resources, capacity,

and institutional will to adopt holistic, interdisciplinary, and transformative approaches to teaching and learning. Furthermore, the diversity of cultural, economic, and political contexts across countries necessitates flexible and context-sensitive models of educational transformation (Howlett et al., 2016).

This research addresses this need by adopting an integrative systems approach that combines educational theory and innovation metrics. It places particular emphasis on transforming student mindsets—toward sustainability-oriented innovation thinking—as a key outcome of reformed engineering education, contributing to the redefinition of engineering education as a catalyst for societal transformation. This entails adopting roles as facilitators, collaborators, and change agents—capable of leading sustainable innovation processes in diverse and dynamic contexts.

2 Methodology

The research will employ a mixed-methods and practice-oriented approach, incorporating qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques to capture the multifaceted nature of the learning process involving experimental interventions with engineering students. This process involves four stages: literature review, approach design, implementation and evaluation, and framework refining (Boud & Solomon, 2001; de Ven, 2007).

This work is in progress, specifically in the first stage, where was developed a systematic literature review (SLR) following the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines to ensure transparency, reproducibility, and reliability in analyzing innovation, sustainability, and engineering education (Page et al., 2021; Petticrew & Roberts, 2006). The methodology follows four stages: identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion, enabling a structured approach to recognize research trends, gaps, and methodological insights (Boland et al., 2017).

A preliminary exploratory search was conducted using Google Scholar to define relevant keywords based on three core concepts of the groups: innovation, sustainability, and engineering education. The search equation was iteratively refined to align with the research questions:

- i. How has the academic discourse on innovation and sustainability within engineering education developed over the past decade, and what trends characterize this knowledge production?
- ii. Which student-centered pedagogical approaches and educational resources are most frequently implemented to foster innovation capabilities to address sustainability challenges in engineering education?
- iii. To what extent are innovation outcomes articulated in alignment with sustainability objectives in the reviewed literature, and how is this relationship conceptualized?
- iv. What are the dominant findings, insights, and implications drawn from the literature regarding integrating innovation and sustainability in engineering education?

Scopus and ERIC databases were selected for the formal search process. The search equation integrated key terms related to the three groups, focusing on publications from 2015 to 2024 to align with the 2030 agenda framework. The process identified 187 documents (138 from Scopus, 49 from ERIC). After temporal filtering, 34 papers were excluded. Additional exclusion criteria (duplicates, document type, and thematic relevance) reduced the dataset to 63 final sources: 25 from Scopus, 29 from ERIC, and 9 obtained through snowball sampling.

The study for selected literature considers a multi-level analysis approach, providing a structure to scaffold how the documents conceptualize innovation for sustainability in engineering education. It ensures a comprehensive understanding of its implementation across different scales of influence, as is depicted in Figure 1, which examines the results across three analytical levels: macro, meso, and micro (Courgeau, 2003).

At the macro level, the study investigates the interconnections between innovation, sustainability, and education in the selected literature. This level of analysis examines how overarching institutional and policy

frameworks impact the integration of sustainability into engineering curricula. The focus is on understanding how innovation culture and skill development contribute to sustainability-oriented education.

At the meso level, the analysis centers on how innovation supports sustainability through design approaches and resource efficiency in engineering education. This includes exploring curriculum transformation, adaptation, and the diffusion of best practices. Additionally, this level examines the role of student-centered pedagogies, particularly project-based and experiential learning, in preparing future engineers to address sustainability challenges.

Figure 1. Methodological process

Finally, at the micro level, the study delves into specific themes and contextual factors influencing sustainability in engineering education. This includes analyzing technological adoption, industry-academia collaboration, experiential learning, and stakeholder engagement. The study also considers the importance of long-term impact, scalability, and ethical considerations, which are crucial in shaping effective and sustainable engineering education models.

3 Results

The study reveals how institutional culture, language, teaching practices, and contextual conditions shape the integration of sustainability vision into innovation in engineering education through a multi-level analysis, examining macro, meso, and micro levels.

At the macro level, a significant finding regards the institutional vision and national policy frameworks in defining the direction and scope of sustainability education. Universities that embed sustainability within their strategic objectives tend to foster a culture conducive to innovation and interdisciplinary collaboration (Georgallis & Bruijn, 2022; Küçüksayraç & Ariburun Kirca, 2020). However, a recurring challenge is the lack of a standardized language to articulate sustainability goals, which limits coherence across institutional and geographical boundaries (Persson et al., 2023). The fragmented use of terminology undermines knowledge transfer and creates barriers to curriculum alignment, particularly in international or collaborative educational programs (Sterling et al., 2018). This absence of a shared vocabulary hampers the development of a unified educational strategy for sustainability, which is critical for shaping innovation-oriented engineering graduates.

Skill development emerges as another macro-level concern, with several studies emphasizing the importance of cultivating transversal competencies such as systems thinking, ethical reasoning, and collaborative problem-solving. These skills are increasingly considered fundamental to sustainability education and linked to broader discourses on employability and innovation capacity (Blocker, 2023). Institutional efforts to develop such competencies are often shaped by external frameworks such as the United Nations Sustainable Development

Goals (SDGs). However, local interpretations of these frameworks vary (Georgallis & Bruijn, 2022; Persson et al., 2023).

At the meso level, curricular innovation is a mechanism for embedding sustainability in engineering education. Student-centered approaches are recurrently cited as effective strategies for fostering student engagement and developing sustainability-related skills (Pineda et al., 2024; Sonetti et al., 2019). However, successful implementation depends heavily on institutional culture and faculty readiness. Cultural resistance to interdisciplinary teaching and rigid departmental structures remains significant barriers (Moreno-Serna et al., 2022; Schönach et al., 2023). The literature highlights the need for structured faculty development programs that build educators' capacity to teach across disciplinary boundaries and adopt student-centered approaches (Amos & Levinson, 2019; Rekalde-Rodríguez et al., 2023).

Teacher training is an emerging issue that is becoming a growing demand for preparation in sustainability topics and student-centered approaches. This situation limits the depth and consistency of sustainability integration in engineering programs (Chen et al., 2019; Schönach et al., 2023). Several studies advocate for teacher education reforms that include sustainability-focused pedagogical frameworks, continuous professional development, and institutional incentives for interdisciplinary teaching (Das Neves et al., 2021; de Kraker et al., 2017). Moreover, the promotion of collaborative teaching cultures, where faculty from diverse disciplines co-develop and co-deliver sustainability content, is suggested as a strategy to overcome disciplinary silos and foster innovation (Egelund Holgaard et al., 2016).

At the micro level, the findings emphasize the influence of local context in shaping how sustainability is understood and implemented into innovation in engineering education. Factors such as regional sustainability challenges, institutional priorities, and stakeholder expectations all impact curriculum design and pedagogical choices (Howard et al., 2021; Murcott, 2016). The engagement of students and external partners in sustainability initiatives—through internships, service learning, or community projects—enhances relevance and deepens learning outcomes (Breen et al., 2023; Iyer-Raniga & Andamon, 2016). However, scalability remains challenging, particularly when such initiatives are resource-intensive or rely on individual champions.

In this context, language and discourse significantly shape pedagogical outcomes at the micro level. The way sustainability is framed within courses, learning outcomes, and institutional documents influences students' perceptions and pedagogical practices. Some studies suggest that overly technical or vague language can alienate students and obscure the ethical and societal dimensions of sustainability (Sierra et al., 2022; Sterling et al., 2018). Therefore, aligning language use with educational objectives and disciplinary norms is essential for fostering meaningful engagement.

Finally, ethical considerations and long-term impact are recurrent themes throughout the literature. Sustainable engineering education is not solely about technical competence but also about instilling a sense of social responsibility and environmental stewardship. These outcomes require sustained institutional commitment, flexible curricular models, and a willingness to adapt to evolving sustainability challenges (Sims et al., 2021; Wagner et al., 2021).

4 Concluding Remark

Empowering Engineers for Long-Term Societal Impact

The reviewed literature reflects a shared recognition of the urgent need to prepare engineering graduates for long-term engagement with sustainability challenges. While numerous pedagogical initiatives have introduced innovation and sustainability into the engineering classroom, empirical evidence regarding their enduring impact on students' professional practice remains limited. This underscores the need for longitudinal studies

that explore how graduates apply sustainability competencies in their careers and how educational institutions can better support this transition. Moreover, fostering self-awareness and mindset transformation is central to effective learning. Educational models should more explicitly integrate reflective practices, enabling students to internalize sustainability values and navigate ethical tensions inherent in engineering decisions.

Contextualizing Innovation through Language, Culture, and Stakeholder Synergy

Sustainability innovation could be interpreted through cultural, political, and institutional contexts. The literature reveals substantial variation in how sustainability is conceptualized and operationalized across regions and disciplines. A major barrier to implementation is the absence of a shared vocabulary and aligned long-term vision among stakeholders. Engineers, educators, industry leaders, and policymakers often operate within parallel discourses that limit collaboration and innovation diffusion. Addressing this fragmentation requires deliberate efforts to co-create a common language of sustainability—grounded in systems thinking, ethics, and cultural relevance.

Investing in Educators as Agents of Change

Educators are the linchpins of sustainability and innovation promotion in education, they demand training, institutional support, and pedagogical practice to lead them in their classrooms. Beyond technical expertise, teachers must adopt the role of facilitators and experts—mentors who guide students through complex, interdisciplinary problems with societal relevance—. This facilitative role enhances critical reflection, ethical reasoning, and collaborative problem-solving—skills essential for addressing sustainability challenges in engineering practice. To realize this potential, faculty development must become a strategic priority, moving beyond isolated training sessions toward sustained, context-sensitive support mechanisms embedded in institutional cultures.

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